

EFFECT OF BOTANICALS AND SYNTHETIC INSECTICIDES ON INSECT PEST AND DISEASES OF MARIGOLD

Akinkunmi, O.Y, Arogundade, O and Fajinmi, O.B.
National Horticultural Research Institute P.M.B. 5432, Ibadan, Nigeria.

ABSTRACT

The experiment was conducted in the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT) Idi-Ishin, Ibadan to determine the efficacy of the botanicals and synthetic insecticide in controlling the pests and reducing the manifestation of diseases in Marigold. The experiment was arranged in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replicates. Extracts from *Chrysanthemum morifolli* (garden mum) leaf extracts (100 g/litre), *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) leaf extracts (200 g/litre), *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seeds extract (5 ml/10litres) and Cypermethrin (synthetic insecticide 5 ml/10litres of water) were applied as foliar sprays 2, 5 and 7 weeks after transplanting using a hand sprayer. The control plots were without botanicals or any insecticide application. Aphids and *Alternaria* blight were identified as the major insect pest and fungal disease. The number of aphids was significantly ($P < 0.05$) lower in the treated plots than in the control. However, of all the botanicals, *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seed oil extracts significantly reduced aphids population and disease incidence compared with the *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) and *Chrysanthemum morifolli* (garden mum) leaf extract. The plant height, number of leaves, number of flowers and seed weight were significantly higher in plots sprayed with Cypermethrin and lowest in the control plots. In the result neem seed extract performed best among the botanicals and was comparable with cypermethrin in the plant height and number of flowers and the reduction in the percentage incidence of disease on marigold and could therefore be used as an alternative to cypermethrin in marigold production.

KEYWORDS: *Alternaria* blight, Aphids, *Chrysanthemum*, Neem, *Tithonia*

INTRODUCTION

Marigold (*Tagetes erecta*) also known as "African giant" is hardy, continuously blooming plants that come in several bright and attractive colors, primarily yellow, orange and maroon which are useful in floral arrangement. It is an ornamental annual plant, easily grown and can tolerate any climatic condition. Marigold plants do well in rich, well drained soil but are tolerant to average slightly poor soil. Apart from its aesthetic value, its medicinal and nematocidal properties also distinguished it as an economic plant. (Olabiyi and Oyedunmade, 2007), *T. erecta* has been known to be a natural insecticide and it is used as companion plant in controlling insect pests in vegetable fields (Weaver, *et al*, 1994). However, marigold is being attacked by insects that act as vectors in transmitting some viral and fungal diseases (Chase *et al.*, 1995). Among the pathogens affecting marigold plants are fungi, viruses, nematodes and bacteria.

Pests and diseases are part of nature; the aim of natural control is to maintain a natural balance between pests and predators and to keep pests and diseases down to an acceptable level within the ecosystem.

Research focus are already shifting towards natural plant products such as biological pesticides because of their ability to produce environmentally friendly and efficacious chemical substances (Schmutterer, 1990) in order to reduce the harmful effect of synthetic pesticides on our environment in the course of controlling the incidence of pest and diseases on our crops. Perich *et al*, (1994) also noted that plant derived products are increasingly being used to combat crop pests because they are natural and are often assumed to be safe for the environment while Jackai *et al*, 1992 envisaged that natural plant products would replace or minimize the use of highly toxic and persistent synthetic chemicals. This study was therefore aimed at determining the efficacy of the botanicals in comparison with a well known and proven synthetic insecticide in controlling the attack of insects and diseases manifestation in marigold.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was conducted in the floriculture garden of the National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Idi-Ishin, Ibadan to determine the efficacy of the botanicals and synthetic insecticide in controlling insects and the manifestation of diseases in marigold. Marigold seeds were raised in trays in the nursery for six weeks and were thereafter transplanted to the field. The plot size was a 2m × 2m with 1m furrow between each bed. The plant was spaced 1m × 1m apart to give a total population of 10,000 plants/ha. The experiment was arranged in a Randomized Complete Block Design (RCBD) and replicated three times. Fresh leaves of *Chrysanthemum morifolli* (garden mum) and *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) were collected and dried, after which they were milled into powder form. Also *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seeds were collected, washed and dried. The seed coats were then removed after which it was milled into powder form. Extracts were made from the blended *Chrysanthemum* and *Tithonia* leaves by the addition of water and carefully sieving the filtrates with a clean sieve. Also the neem seed oil was extracted in a soxhlet extractor using ethanol as the solvent. Samples of infected leaves of marigold plants were collected from the plots and washed with tap water. The leaves were then cut into 5 mm segments and surfaced sterilized in 70 % ethanol before rinsing in three changes of sterile distilled water and blotted dry with sterile Whiteman No 1 filter paper. The sterilized leaves were aseptically placed on plates of sterilized potato Dextrose Agar (PDA). Incubation of the inoculated medium was done at 28 ± 2°C for five days. Sub-culturing was also done until pure cultures of the isolate were obtained and thereafter kept on slant of PDA in MacCartney bottle. The identification of the isolate was carried out using colony morphology and microscopic characteristics.

The three plants extracts; *Chrysanthemum morifolli* (garden mum) leaf extracts (100 g/litre), *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) leaf extracts (200 g/litre), *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seeds extract (5 ml/10litres) and Cypermethrin (synthetic insecticide 5 ml/10litres of water) were applied at 2, 5 and 7 WAT as foliar sprays using a hand sprayer. Control plots without any insecticide applications were also maintained. Insects were handpicked from the plants at the early hours of the day. Insect population, disease incidence, plant height, number of leaves, number of flowers per plant were taken fortnightly by sampling the foliage of four randomly selected plants per plot, while seed weight was assessed and expressed as grams per plot. Collected data was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and the means of significant tests were separated using Least Significant difference (LSD) at P < 0.05 probability level.

The incidence of diseases was estimated every two weeks from the fourth week after transplanting till the eight week after transplanting. The percentage disease incidence was determined using the formula:

$$\frac{\text{Number of infected (symptomatic) plants/bed} \times 100}{\text{Population of plants/bed}}$$

RESULTS

The major insect pest observed on the marigold plants are Aphids (*Aphis craccivora*). The other insect pest whose occurrences were sporadic and very low at the period of the study is *Zonocerus variegatus* (variegated grasshopper). The number of aphids was significantly (P < 0.05) lower in the treated plots than in the control. Cypermethrin (synthetic insecticide) significantly reduced the aphids' population to the lowest level on the sprayed plots compared with other treatments but the aphids population was not significantly different from that of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seed oil at 2, 6 and 8 weeks after transplanting. However, of all the botanicals, neem seed oil extract significantly reduced aphids population better when compared with the *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) and *Chrysanthemum morifolli* leaf extracts (Table 1). The plant height, number of leaves, number of flowers and seed weight of marigold were significantly higher in plots sprayed with Cypermethrin at 4 and 6WAT compared with other treatments and lowest values were observed in the control plots (Tables 2). The plant height of the control was not significantly different from that of *Chrysanthemum* at 4 and 6 WAT likewise the number of leaves observed with the application of *Chrysanthemum* and control were not significantly different at 4 WAT. Among the botanicals neem seed oil extract had a significantly higher plant height and number of flowers 4WAT compared with *Tithonia diversifolia* (tithonia) and *Chrysanthemum morifolli*. For the number of leaves, neem seed oil extract was significantly higher compared with other botanicals 4WAT but was not significantly different from other botanicals at 6WAT. The seed weight of the marigold plant was significantly higher with the application of cypermethrin compared with other treatments while a significantly lower seed weight was observed in the control (Table 2).

The isolated pathogen was identified as *Alternaria alternata* which caused blight (a fungal disease) on marigold plants. The manifestation of stunted growth and mottling on the leaves of some plants revealed the presence of virus on such plants. The percentage incidence of disease was significantly lower with the application of cypermethrin compared with other treatments at 4, 6 and 8 WAT but this was not significantly different from the percentage incidence of disease observed with the application of neem seed oil extract at 4 and 6 WAT (Table 3). The highest percentage disease incidence was observed in the control.

DISCUSSION

From the result, Cypermethrin had the greatest effect in reducing the population of aphids, with an increase in the plant height, number of leaves, number of flowers, and seed weight of marigold plant. Like other synthetic pesticides, they are most effective in controlling pests. Shankara Naika *et al.*, (2005) noted that they can also kill pests' natural predators and could cause a serious resurgence of some pests when not applied at the right time, in the right way and in the right dosage rate per hectare. Being a synthetic insecticide, they are toxic to human health, animals and the environment and as such may not be recommended as an effective insecticide to farmers. Natural plant extracts (botanicals) on the other hand, are suitable for organic farming, cheaper, environmentally friendly with no hazardous effect on animals and human health and also effective in reducing the population of pest and disease incidence on plants. In the result, *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seed extract performed best among the botanicals used in the control of the insects and as such helped in reducing the incidence of disease of the plant. This could be due to the presence of (phytochemicals) in neem and it corroborates the findings of Umar *et al.*, 2002 and Makeri *et al.*, 2007 who noted that Azadirachtin extracts from the seeds, leaves and bark of the Neem tree has been reported to have strong biological activities against insect pests, but with very low toxicity to mammals and the environment generally. Akol *et al.*, 2001 also noted that registered Neem insecticide formulations Neemros[®] and Neemroc EC[®] have also been found to be effective against insect pests of vegetables but safe to their natural enemies. Natarajan *et al.* 2003 and Subapriya and Nagini (2005) also noted that Neem elaborates a vast array of biologically active compounds that are chemically diverse and structurally complex and that more than 140 compounds have been isolated from different parts of neem. Neem seed extract, in this work, was comparable with cypermethrin in the plant height and number of flowers and the reduction in insect population and the percentage incidence of disease on marigold.

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained, *Azadirachta indica* (neem) seed extracts being the most effective botanical and environmentally friendly could serve as an alternative in controlling aphids and in turn could help in reducing the incidence of Alternaria blight, and virus on marigold plants in fields where aphids serve as vectors.

REFERENCE:

- Akol, A.M., Sithanatham, S, Varela, A.M., Mueke, J.M. and Okelo, R.O. (2001). Evaluation of two neem insecticides for non- target effects on the larval parasitoids of the diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.).
- Chase, A.R., Daughtry, M and Simone, G.W. (1995). Diseases of annuals and perennials. *Ball Publishing*, Batavia. 111. 202pp.
- Jackai, L.W.N., Inang, E.E. and Nwobi, P. (1992). The potential for controlling post-flowering pests of cowpea, *Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp using neem, *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss. *Tropical Pest Management*, 38 (1) 56-60.
- Makeri, H.K., Maikai, V.A. and Nok, J.A. (2007). Effect of topical application of neem seed (*Azadirachta indica*) extract on sheep infested with *Amblyomma variegatum*. *African Journal of Biotechnology*. 6(20):2324-2327.
- Natarajan, V. Venugopal, P.V. and Meon T. (2003). Effect of *Azadirachta indica* (neem) on the growth pattern of dermatophytes. *Indian J. Med. Microbiol.* 1 (2):98-101.
- Olabiya, T.I and Oyedunmade, E.E.A. (2007). Marigold (*Tagetes erecta* L.) as interplant with cowpea for the control of nematode pests. *African Crop Sci. Confr. Proceedings*. Vol.8 pp 1075-1078.
- Perich, J.M.C., Bertsch and Tredway (1994). Toxicity from three *Tagetes* against adults and larvae of yellow fever mosquito and anopheles stephensi (Diptera: Culicidae). *J. Med. Entomology*. 31:833-837.

Schmutterer, H. (1990). Properties and potential of natural pesticides for the neem tree, *Azadirachta indica* Ann. Rev. Entomology 35, 271-298.

Shankara, Naika, Joep van Lidt de Jeude, Marja de Goffau, Martin Hilmi, Barbara van Dam. (2005). Pests and Diseases of Tomato: In Cultivation of tomato (Production, Processing and Marketing). Barbara van Dan (ed.) Agromisa Foundation and CTA, Wageningen, Netherlands. Pg 37-59.

Subapriya, R. and Nagini, S. (2005). Medicinal properties of neem leaves. *Curr. Med.Chem. Anticancer agent* 5 (2): 149 -156.

Umar, A., Abdulrahman, H.T. and Kokori, M. (2002). Preliminary studies of the efficacies of the aqueous extracts of leaf and seed kernel of Neem (*Azadirachta indica* A. Juss) for the control of cowpea bruchid *Callobruchus maculatus* (Coleoptera:Bruchidae). *Research Journal of Science* 8(1&2):25-30.

Weaver, D.K., Wells, C.D., Dunkel, F.V, and Bertsch, S.E. (1994). Insecticidal activity of foliar and root extracts of *Tagetes minuta* against adult Mexican bean weevils (Coleoptera: Bruchidae). *J. Econ. Entomology*. 87:1718-1725.

Table 1: Effect of insecticides application on aphid populations per plot.

Treatments	Weeks after transplanting			
	2	4	6	8
Neem	2.00c	4.00c	4.67c	4.67cd
Tithonia	4.00b	4.67bc	9.00b	9.10bc
Chrysanthemum	5.00b	6.33b	9.67b	9.70b
Cypermethrin	0.67c	1.33d	2.00c	2.10d
Control	8.67a	10.33a	21.00a	23.00a

Means with the same letters along the columns are not significantly different at P< 0.05

Table 2: Effect of insecticides application on plant height, number of leaves, Number of flowers and seed weight.

Treatments	Plant height (cm)		Number of leaves		Number of flowers		Seed weight (g/plot)
	4WAT	6WAT	4WAT	6WAT	4WAT	6WAT	
Neem	71.93b	84.50b	84.33b	76.33bc	25.7b	43.7b	46.33b
Tithonia	49.00c	74.67c	67.00c	84.67b	20.3c	32.3c	33.67c
Chrysanthemum	32.33d	42.00d	60.67c	63.33bc	15.7d	21.6d	26.70d
Cypermethrin	88.33a	100.97a	101.67a	169.00a	36.0a	50.7a	52.67a
Water (Control)	30.67d	39.67d	36.00d	26.67c	10.0e	14.7e	15.50e

Means with the same letters along the columns are not significantly different at P< 0.05.

Table 3: Effect of insecticide application on the percentage diseases incidence in marigold

Treatments	Weeks after transplanting		
	4	6	8
Neem	4.67c	11.33ab	17.00a
Tithonia	3.33c	12.76ab	17.00a
Chrysanthemum	6.33b	11.33ab	18.80a
Cypermethrin	3.03c	5.04b	7.06b
Water (Control)	9.67a	15.76a	21.45a

Means with the same letters along the columns are not significantly different at $P < 0.05$.

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Corresponding author

Akinkunmi, O.Y,

National Horticultural Research Institute P.M.B. 5432, Ibadan, Nigeria.

E-mail address: frankrose2@yahoo.com